

AYURVEDIC MANAGEMENT OF ASHMARI W.R.S. RENAL CALCULUS – A SINGLE CASE STUDY***¹Dr. Tejaswini Bhikaji Patil, ²Dr. Meenakshi Rewdkar Kole, ³Dr. Bharat Kadlaskar**¹M.D. Final Year, Ayachikitsa, R.A. Podar Medical College Worli, Mumbai.²Assistant Professor Kayachikitsa, R.A. Podar Medical College Worli, Mumbai.³Head of Department, Kayachikitsa, R.A. Podar Medical College, Worli, Mumbai.

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ABSTRACT

Ashmari is a disease related to urinary system (Mutravaha Strotas). Mutrashmari is explained under Asthamahagad in Ayurveda. Instead of hydrotherapy and other allopathic line of treatment, treatment of this particular case has been planned with Basti karma and other ayurvedic ashmaribhedan and ashmarihar dravya. A 46-year-old female visited OPD with USG abdomen pelvis report showing calculus measuring 7.9 mm in size impacted in the pelviureteric junction of left kidney. She was complaining of pain radiating from left loin region to groin, dysuria, nausea, heaviness in hypogastric region. The patient was admitted in IPD and treated with Yogbasti krama of Dashmul kwath niruh and sahachar tail anuvasan basti. Sthanik snehan swedan (kati sthani) done prior to basti. Internal medications administered were 1) Gokshuradi guggul 250 mg twice in a day after meal 2) Varunadi kwath 30 ml twice a day (containing Varun, pashanbhed, trinpanchmool, gokshur,

yavakshar). The patient was advised to follow diet and lifestyle modification. She got relief in signs and symptoms after treatment. The USG report showed comment of calculus not seen after ayurvedic treatment for 10 days.

KEYWORDS – Ashmari, basti.

INTRODUCTION

Renal calculi are a common problem due to changing lifestyles. It is recurrent in nature. The cases of renal calculi are mostly seen at age of 20-40 years and decline with over 50 years. Modern science stresses various factors like genetics, age, sex, metabolic disorders, sedentary lifestyle, dehydration, the mineral content of water, nutritional deficiency etc. for urinary stone formation. Urolithiasis causes pain, loss of working time, medical expenses, need for hospitalization and an infrequent reason for renal failure. In modern science, the best possible management for urinary calculus is the use of drugs to correct the involved pathologies and use of diuretics as well as surgical intervention including open surgery, percutaneous techniques etc. Renal stone is resembling Ashmari in Ayurveda. Ashmari is the disease that is coming under the Asthamahagad (difficult to cure). Ashmari is vyadhi which is considered under Mutravaha Strotas. As Basti come under Trimarma (threefold of Life) so Acharya Sushruta described Ashmari as darun (fatal) disease. Acharya Sushruta has been described as various medicines as well as surgical intervention for Vrikkashmari. Medicinal treatment is advised to be undertaken in the early stages of the disease. Indication of surgical management has been suggested along with a note of caution for complications. Surgical treatment must be accepted only on failure of conservative treatment and when death becomes inevitable. In Ayurveda, 4 types of Ashmari are described by Acharyas. Vatajasmari, Pittaj Ashmari, Kaphaj Ashmari and shukraj Ashmari. structure and symptoms are different. Vataj Ashmari symptoms resemble with Calcium Oxalate type Stone, Pittaj Ashmari. symptoms resemble with Uric Acid type stone, Kaphaj Ashmari symptoms resemble with oxalate and phosphate stones.

CASE STUDY

A 46 years old female patient came to OPD with symptoms of

- 1) Pain radiating from left loin to groin region
- 2) Nausea
- 3) Dysuria
- 4) Heaviness in hypogastric region.

In the last 15 days.

Patient was admitted to IPD of kayachikitsa department.

History of present illness

Patient was apparently alright before 15 days. For 15 days she experienced radiating pain from left loin region to groin region, nausea, dysuria, heaviness in abdomen. She had taken opinion of allopathic doctor and diagnosed as Renal calculus. For that she has been advised lithotripsy but unwilling to do so.

Past History

N/K/C/O- DM, HTN, BA, PTB

H/O- Renal calculus in both kidneys, treated with hydrotherapy.

S/H/O -Tonsillectomy done at the age of 10 years.

N/H/O – Blood transfusion, PR bleeding.

S/E

RS – AEBE clear

CVS – S1S2 normal

CNS – conscious and oriented

Pallor -absent

Icterus -absent

GIT – liver, spleen, kidneys – nonpalpable

Personal History

Marital status - married

Addiction - Tobacco chewing

Family History

Father - NIL

Mother - NIL

Ashthvidh Pariksha

Nadi – kaph pitta Pradhan tridoshaj

Mala- samyak

Mutra – sashul mutrapravartan

Jivha – ishat saam

Shabd – prakrit

Sparsh – ushna

Drik – prakrit

Akruti – madhyam

O/E (On Examination)

BP -120/70 mm of Hg

Pulse - 88/min

SPO2 -99 % on RA

Temperature – 98.3 F

RBS – 116 mg/dl

USG abdomen and pelvis – 22/05/2025

Left pelviureteric junction calculus measuring 7.9 mms with resultant mild hydronephrosis as described above.

Samprapti

MATERIALS AND METHODS

1. Yogbasti karma – Niruh basti with Dashmul kwath.

Anuvasan basti with sahachar tail.

2. Sthanik snehan swedan – kati sthani

Sr.No.	Name of drugs	Dose of drugs	Kala	Frequency
1	Gokshuradi Guggul	250 mg	After food	Twice a day With lukewarm water.
2	Varunadi kwath	30 ml	After food	Twice a day

RESULT

USG abdomen and pelvis

Before (22/05/2025)	After (02/06/2025)
The ultrasound examination reveals a Left pelvi Ureteric Junction (PUJ). Calculus measuring 7.9 mms with resultant mild Hydronephrosis.	Normal Ultrasound examination of the urinary tract. The left PUJ Calculus is not seen suggesting its passage.

DISCUSSION

Ashmari is vyadhi of Mutravaha strotas. The description of Ashmari vyadhi described by Charaka, Sushrut, Vagbhata. In Asanshodhil (regular not doing Panchkarma) and apthykari (Unwholesome Diet) person Aggravated Kapha Dosha mix up with Mutra (urine) enter in Basti (Kidney, ureter, Bladder) obstruct the urinary tract create Ashmari. Sushrut has clearly mentioned who do not undergo Panchkarma Treatment regularly and who take Unwholesome Diet, follow faulty life style are prone for recurrent kidney stones.

Samprapti Ghatak

Dosha-kaph, pitta, vaat

Dushya-Mutra

Type-Sang

Adhishthan-Basti

Strotas-Mutravaha

Agni-Jathargnimandya, Dhatvagni mandya

Marga-Abhyantar

Action of Medicine

1) Gokshuradi guggul

It contains Gokshur, guggul, triphala, trikatu, musta.

This kalp work as Dhatvagni deepan, bastishodhan, ashmarihar, mutravirechan kalp. Gokshur is avayav rasayan for mutravah strotas specially for Vrikka. it regulates the parisraavan and shoshan karma of Vrikka.

2) Varunadi kwath

It contains Varun, pashanbhed, gokshur, shunthi, trinpanchmool, yavakshar. It works by Ashmari bhedan action. ksharan karm that is gradual detoriation in sanghathan of Ashmari is done by yavakshar. This medicine breaks the Ashmari into smaller particles that could easily pass through the urinary tract.

3) dashmool kwath – sahachar tail Yogbasti kram

Basti works to bring back vitiated vaat dosha to its normal anulom gati and in natural state. It regulates normal mutravahan and mutrapravartan actions. dashmul works as tridoshaghna. Sthanik snehan swedan is done at lowerback region prior to basti.

CONCLUSION

From this study it is clear that Ashmari cases can be managed with Ayurved treatment if size is small. Although Acharya Sushruta has suggested surgery if Ashmari cases not relieved by shaman Treatment but before going to surgery Ayurved Shaman treatment along with basti karm should be try.

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